

Disclosure of technical solutions of tunnels by the press as the decisive factor for the insertion of underground works in feasibility studies of road connections for Vitória, ES.

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ABSTRACT: Espírito Santo, one of the smallest states in Brazil, does not have any tradition in underground works for road infrastructure. Bridges are the unique type of structure adopted in its intersections and connections. The Greater Vitória is demanding new connections for its cities: Vila Velha, Vitória and Cariacica. The public authorities have been proposed again only bridges for these new connections, excluding completely the underground solutions, neither conventional nor Immersed Tunnels. To change this culture many reports in newspapers and magazine were published by the local press to present for the Capixabas the possibilities of tunneling. The first task of the reports was dismissing the myths about tunnels, said even by the local leaders as “a solution too expensive or technically impossible to construct”. The success of this endeavor is proved by the last governmental actions: detailed designs were hired to develop road connections with five tunnels.

1 INTRODUCTION

The society advances culturally as the country increases the general level of education. The technical community can develop itself in many fields with the participation of new engineers, experts and researchers.

The Espírito Santo State is one of the smallest states of Brazil. Vitória is its political capital, a historical city craved over an island surrounded by the municipalities of Vila Velha, Cariacica and Serra.

Espírito Santo does not have any tradition in underground works for urban or non-urban infrastructure. None of its connections or intersections was built with the tunneling technique.

Since the year of 2004 the society of the Greater Vitória has been claiming for a better quality of the transportation system. The initial perception and common sense of the society direct the attentions toward the poor infrastructure of roads. The lack of new roads and connection has been taken as the main

cause of the precarious quality of the traffic and the duration of the bus trips.

1.1 Vitória and the Greater Vitória

The geographic configuration of the Vitória island compresses the roads system to the borders. Prandina (2009a) presented the Figure 1, showing the contours of the coast. Vitória can not count with 32% of its west central area for the city development. There is a central rock massif very steep where any kind of infrastructure for roads had been built yet.

Figure 1. The central rock massif of Vitória

Greater Vitória is the so called metropolitan region with 1.7 (IBGE, 2010) million inhabitants. It includes the already cited municipalities and more 3 ones (Viana, Guarapari and Fundão).

The city of Vitória is the 10th densest city of Brazil with 3.3 million inh./ km². All the others cities have a complementary role in the economic activities comparing to Vitória, and therefore the city is the main actor of trip generation in the metropolitan area. The jobs density showed in Figure 2 (PDTU, 1998) can give the real scenario of its importance.

Figure 2. Jobs per zone – Greater Vitória (PDTU, 1998)

1.2 The Road Infrastructure

The road system of Vitória can be observed in the Figure 3 (PDTU, 1998). Two main road arterial systems can be considered: i) the peripheral ring adjacent to the sea; and ii) the interior system with two main directions.

1.3 The Bridges for the Connections

The range of 150 to 1500 m separates Vitória from continent. The lower sea distances are placed in the northeast of the island and the larger ones are in the southwest.

In the south region are located the existing connections: i) First Bridge, Florentino Avidos; ii) Second Bridge, which can connect 3 cities (Vitória, Vila Velha and Cariacica); iii) Third Bridge, Darcy Castello de Mendonça.

The north connections of the island and the continent are also 3 bridges, but they are not important in terms of length. These bridges are all inside the limits of Vitória.

Figure 3. The arterial system of Vitória (PDTU, 1998)

1.4 The local experience

The construction and engineering companies established in Espírito Santo are experienced in design and construction of small bridges and viaducts.

The local universities have never offered any regular courses in tunnel engineering.

The public authorities have never inspected, leaded or promoted a tunnel construction.

Probably these are the main reasons that explain why all the proposals for new connections were settled in bridge solution.

2 THE ANNOUNCED NEW BRIDGES

New proposals for connections for the Greater Vitória were announced by the governmental authorities in 2008. Before this announce, the Immersed Tunnel proposal for a new connection for Vitória and Vila Velha was released by Kneib (2001a) and (2001b), Kneib and Prandina (2004), Kneib (2005), Kneib (2006), and Casilhas (2007). All of them have shown the possibilities of the tunnel solutions. Despite of these publications, the feasibility studies of new connections for Vila Velha and Cariacica with Vitória did not included any tunnel solutions until 2008, neither Immersed Tunnel nor conventional ones (NATM or TBM).

2.1 The Vitória-Velha 4th Bridge

In 2008 has occurred the first announcement of the 4th bridge for Vitória and Vila Velha connection.

In May of 2008 was announced by the government the launch of the projects of two bridges: the viaduct over Carioca Avenue and the 4th Bridge between Vitória and Vila Velha. Oliveira (2008) registered the authority's speech about these two bridges.

The viaduct over Carioca Avenue was constructed and had started the operation in May, 26th of 2012. Its current volume flow is 120 vehicles per hour in peak hours, 20% of the quantity expected (80% less), as released by Castro (2013).

The construction of the 4th Bridge to connect Vitória and Vila Velha has not happened since 2008. In the other side, the PDTU (1998) had considered as the most priority a new connection between Vitória and Cariacica.

2.2 The Vitória-Cariacica 4th Bridge

A second announcement of a new bridge for the Greater Vitória has happened in September of 2013. Once more, a new 4th Bridge was announced between Vitória and Cariacica (Sá, 2013), the most populated city of the state.

The project design for the so called 4th bridge for Vitória and Cariacica connection was released by the government of Espírito Santo as presented by Sá (2013). This report has shown the functional project and the reference price for the detailed design: US\$ 3.3 million.

According to Rocha (2012) the length of this bridge would be 1,400 m. Sá (2013) presented the estimated price of the work construction: US\$ 240 to US\$ 330 million. Proscholdt *et al.* (2013) reported the cost for the same construction as US\$ 284 million.

2.3 Improvements for the existing Bridges

Both Second and Third bridges have plans issued by their authorities, Rodosol and DNIT respectively, released to society by the press.

According to Jazra (2012), the cost estimation by Dnit for the works of enlargement, maintenance and reinforcement are estimated as US\$ 225 million for a 2,300 m bridge.

Rodosol also has a demand coming from the public authority ARSI (*Agência Reguladora de Saneamento Básico e Infraestrutura Viária*) to

enlarge the Third Bridge, but the cost was not released because there is a discussion between the best project: a new deck of the bridge with a total of 5 or 7 lanes.

This entire scenario created a “traditional existing bridges business” arrangement of engineering companies and authorities.

3 THE SCENARIO FOR TUNNELS

The most notorious manifestation of the society is the general dissatisfaction with the public transportation system, as stated by Pausem and Louzada (2012). Their social research has described a crisis in the urban mobility in Greater Vitória. In the same direction, Pandini (2007) described the general condition of the arterial system as strangled.

Considering the logical of the last paragraphs, the scenario in Espírito Santo for a tunnel solution can be described as follows:

- Any specialized company in tunnels in local technical community;
- Few local engineering companies linked to the bridge business sector;
- Any tunnel construction in Espírito Santo in the road system, even in non-urban areas;
- Any national experience in Immersed Tunnel; But the opportunity for the Immersed Tunnel for the Vitoria connections seem to be obvious and the most suitable solution because the following technical reasons:
 - A bridge, in any position must consider the ship traffic of the ports and future demands of the tourism and industrial transportation options along the bay;
 - The subaquatic distance of a road in Immersed Tunnel would lead to the smallest construction length and, also smallest ramps gradients of any other solution;
 - A geotechnical poor condition for a reasonable geometry for conventional tunnel excavated in soil.

Additionally, the causes of the notorious dissatisfaction of society were reported by the Origin&Destiny research (OD-PMV, 2007): an increase of 67% in the term of the medium car trips and 17% in the buses' between 1998 and 2007.

3.1 Saturated Connections and Perception

The saturation of connections will increase the range time of the peak hours. According to

Kneib (2011) the conditions of the road system saturation is the worst possible for the quality of life in urban areas. And Vitória is facing traffic jams daily in all the access of the road systems.

DaMatta (2008) reported in a deep research that the road traffic in Vitória causes “stress, fatigue, neurosis, and all kind of dangerous and risk”. These issues were confirmed by the observations with cameras which showed the general conflicts between drivers and pedestrians.

The existing bridges itself have more flow capacity than the road system of Vitória. Once the users can not reach them, two times per day, the perception that a new bridge or connection would improve the traffic flow is the first lay conclusion.

Another statement of the negative impact of the traffic conditions in Vitória is given by Caus and Santos (2008). A chaotic scenario is described as the traffic condition. As its consequence, the elevation of the pollution in Vitória and the degradation of the quality of life are the major negative impact. In 2008, the diagnostic of the perception of the society about the quality of the traffic was very poor. After 5 years, the total number of vehicles in the state increased more than 50%, with a peak of growth in 2009 of 13%.

3.2 PDTU 1998

PDTU (1998) is the “urban transportation director plan” for The Greater Vitória, a two year study conducted by the most important authority of research in Espírito Santo, the Jones dos Santos Neves Institute. This study has included a team of local experts in urbanism, transportation engineering and economy.

This study summarized the future 10 years of priorities in infrastructure. It is the most comprehensive technical study to face the growth of The Greater Vitória. The connection predicted and stated as necessary was the 4th Bridge of Vitória and Cariacica (PDTU, 1998). A suggestion for the 5th bridge with 920 m between Vitória and Vila Velha is mentioned, but not as a priority.

This study had shown that in 15 years the number of car trips increased 100%, reaching in 1997 the amount of 506.000 per day in Greater Vitória. In the period of 16 to 20:00 pm the majority of the flow occurs with 206.000 trips, 48.000 in 20 pm the peak flow.

3.3 BRT – A national project in the state

Damasceno (2011) presented the project of BRT (Bus Rapid Transit) system designed for the Greater Vitória and showed the first traces of the 4th Bridge between Vitória and Cariacica. The BRT project for the Greater Vitória is a four step plan and the main axis is defined as showed in the Figure 4. This plan excluded the tunnel connection between Vitória and Vila Velha proposed by the government road department (DER, 2010).

Figure 4. The BRT plan for the Greater Vitória

3.4 The Petroleum Industry

Espírito Santo is one of the most benefited Brazilian states where the latest petroleum announcements of the Pré-sal had great positive expectation impact in terms of increasing of the revenues of the government and the state economic growth itself.

This growth includes importation of middle class due to qualified jobs offered by this industry. The generation of direct and indirect jobs will have as one of its consequences the increase of cars in the urban area. Therefore, the number of trips is the short term negative impact which demands certainly new infrastructure for Greater Victoria. This process is current in progress since 2008 in Espírito Santo.

4 THE STRATEGY FOR TUNNELS

Two myths are present in local technical community: tunnel are too expensive for

Espírito Santo and tunnels are impossible to build in Vitória.

Dismiss the myth that tunnels are technically impossible to construct in Vitória was a very good topic for a initial strategy to insert the tunnel solution in a very inhospitable context, as shown.

A proposal for a tunnel connection would face less difficult if the approach could encounter an ambience with a minimum positive receptivity.

The approach of an “Environmental Era” reported by Assis (2008) is favorable for underground solutions for roads in urban environment. Basically it states that tunnels can put the cars and traffic beneath the earth and leave the surface space for a more convenient activities of people and greened rebuilt areas.

4.1 *The Opportunity for Tunnels in Press*

Casilhas (2007) reproduced the main origin work of Kneib (2001) summarized by Kneib and Prandina (2004) which shows that the most suitable solution for the Vitória and Vila Velha connection is an Immersed Tunnel.

Martins (2008) again reproduced these works, but bringing a new speech of the most important authority of the Espírito Santo state. The vice-governor stated in this report that a study conducted by the government showed that a tunnel was the best solution to connect Vitória and Vila Velha. This was the key to start a good disclosure of the tunnel solution.

4.2 *The First Engineering Report*

Prandina (2008a) presented in the press the international price and term for the immersed tunnel solution to connect Vitória and Vila Velha: US\$ 300 mi project to be constructed in “only” three years. This was the first estimation for a construction presented to the public. And the 3 years term was unusual, because all the big projects which took place in Espírito Santo, the construction works had lasted for more than 10 years.

These real and positive engineering aspects are the biggest in perception for the society and have great impact. The construction industry has effectively a bad reputation in terms of duration of the works over all other economic activities. Therefore, if a solution can avoid these negative aspects, high price and long term, the positive impact could be great.

Prandina (2008a) presented by the press offered the society the data to argue the local technical community why not a tunnel solution had been considered carefully.

The society could realize the tunnel solution for the connection of Vitória and Vila Velha might be very possible, because even a worst number than presented would be a better one than the society had seen in the history of the construction projects.

Prandina (2008a) newspaper article showed the fundamental concepts which were presented in Kneib and Prandina (2004). It has shown the most important aspects of the tunnel solution: i) a low international price comparing to bridges; ii) a short term period for the construction.

One in the society could ask now: Is this proposal suitable? Why our engineers and other professional did not include tunnels as solution for connections?

4.3 *The Economic Impact Subject*

The first opportunity to show how great could be the urgency for new connection in a tunnel between Vitória and Vila Velha came up when Prandina (2008b) presented the very first billionaire number spent by the tow payers of the Third Bridge.

This number showed that in 15 years they would spend R\$ 5.3 Bi, which corrected by the inflation and current rate represents US\$ 3.2 Bi. After this work, many others used this article as motivation of researches and assessments of the road congestions as reference for economic loss in Vitória, as Anselmo Neto *et al.* (2010).

This economic subject with great impact brought the attention of society in general, politicians and technical community: the numbers were very simple and the assessment was showed clearly by the press to the readers. Now they could come up with a logical and touchable number.

The immediate consequence after these publications were new invites to present them the tunnel matters in other media vehicles.

5 DISCLOSING THE TUNNELS

Disclosing the tunnel solution was thought as a best way to offer the society the options available to the connections, since the technical community had been imposing a bad prejudgment to tunnel solution. Once, the importance of the tunnels for Vitória as a

efficient work construction is a useful tool to play the main role in the challenge against current traffic jams.

Prandina (2010a) presented a sketch for the Cauê Tunnel, including all the lanes for BRT and for cars (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. A Cut-and-Cover proposal for the Cauê Tunnel (Prandina, 2010a – Infographics: André Félix)

The natural step was disclosure all the tunnels which might be constructed in Greater Vitória for road infrastructure.

For that purpose the report “Six tunnels against congestions” had accomplished this task. This was the title of the report (Prandina, 2008c) which listed the tunnels: i) The Immersed Tunnel connecting Vitória and Vila Velha (aprox. 1.1 km); ii) A conventional Tunnel through the central massif of the island (2 km); iii) Cesar Hilal Av. Tunnel (600 m); iv) Two conventional tunnels in Serafin Derenzi also in rock (500 and 700 m each); v) Cauê Plaza tunnel to connect the 3rd bridge with its arterial system beneath a residential area (400 m).

Prandina (2008c) was not the first to predict tunnels for Serafim Derenzi and for the central massif. PDTU (1998) suggested this lineation. These are the only 3 tunnels predicted in PDTU (1998).

In terms of comprehensive information and details, the report of the Cauê Tunnel was a remark. The repercussion of this report was so great that in less the one year the government of the state announced it would be constructed.

All of these disclosure informations about tunnels are new subject to the local society and technical community.

One important interview was demanded by the press to explain to the society why do they need the tunnels. Prandina (2009b) presented that the future of the time spent in trips in Vitória would have a strong increase if the road design would not have improvements.

In sequence, the society perception clearly has increased with all these information about new infrastructures.

The proposals were comprehensive and will improve the roads of the public transportation system, since all of them must include the exclusive roads for buses.

Additionally, cars and public transportation system would be beneficiate directly and indirectly by the improvement of the road system. The proofs that these tunnels are suitable for the public purpose relies over the government designed the BRT system, excluding the use of the Vitória Vila Velha Immersed Tunnel.

5.1 The Negative Aspects Strategy

The strategy of listing the negative aspects of the traffic problems in Vitória showed itself very valid. And more opportunities to increase the knowledge of the community were offered by the press that also demanded new reports with the subject.

And therefore more 25 different reports were produced against the great villain of the society quality of mobility: no new connection for the cities of Greater Vitória between 2009 and 2015.

5.2 The First National Seminar in ES

After Prandina (2008a) a seminar called “Túneis para Vitória” counting with national experts in tunneling were offered to local technical community. Rocha (2008) presented the Santos-Guarujá tunnel project, its conception and costs. Assis (2008) presented the trends and challenges of the underground space use. Kochen (2008) presented the historical cases of the immersed tunnels. Kneib (2008) presented the project of 4th connection between Vitória and Vila Velha in Immersed Tunnel. Prandina (2008d) presented the tunnels those are demanded by the road system of Vitória and its efficiency and simplicity to be constructed. Also in this seminar, the press released this event in newspaper and in its web sites.

6 THE EXPECTED CHANGE TO TUNNEL

All the released information by the press has posed the authorities under pressure to answer the obvious question: why not tunnel ?

The logical and expected announcement of the change of the solution from bridge into tunnel was done by Hartung (2009). The state of Espírito Santo, considering the tunnel as possible solution, has decided to change the 4th connection for tunnel one.

This decision was finally materialized in executive actions when the state of Espírito Santo launched the bid to hire the detailed project design for the tunnel (DER, 2010).

Another 4 tunnels released by Prandina (2008c) had each one its bid to hire the detailed project announced, excepting the tunnel through the central rock massif.

Therefore, a total of 5 designs of different tunnels, for different road systems have been hired by the public authorities.

6.1 The tunnel announced and the tow

The tunnel announced by the government (Hartung, 2009) connects the same regions (neighborhoods) of Vitória and Vila Velha of the tunnel suggested by Kneib (2001), using in Vila Velha the same streets to disperse the traffic that comes from Vitória. The axis of the government's proposal is near (50 to 100 m) to the one proposed by Kneib and Prandina (2004). Although, the construction method of the government's proposal is different: the construction method is a NATM. The initial geology presented in the geophysics tests performed previously obligated the depth to pass through the bed rock. Therefore, the tunnel floor is located deeper than 50 m (-52.154 m) as showed in the Functional Design (DER, 2010).

Also the government stated that the tunnel must be financed in part with a direct tow which could be one of the items of a Brazilian PPP (private-public partnership).

6.2 The comprehensive proposal – No Tow

In order to offer an opportunity to the state to construct the tunnel proposed by Kneib and Prandina (2004) without a tow, Prandina (2010b) presented a proposal to use the land of a low density populated area at Prainha da Glória and vicinity for expansion of the realty market to create a new neighborhood.

It included an area around 500.000 m² and a land reclamation of 100.000 m².

This proposal has a simple concept: the city of Vila Velha and the state of Espírito Santo legalize the area and build the embankment to achieve the land reclamation. Realty market or construction companies buy the land from the city to build and the direct revenues are used to finance the construction and the part of the taxes are used to maintenance.

7 THE PROPOSED NATM TUNNEL

The conception of the conventional tunnel in NATM proposed by the government of the state (DER,2010) requested a deep depth to ensure its viability. The total depth of more than 50 m lead to severe vertical ramps for the roads of 6 % in the side of Vitória (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Geometry sections of Vitória and Vila Velha conventional tunnel in NATM (modified - DER, 2010)

According to Ford (1997) if a loaded truck in 60 km/h starts an uphill displacement, after 500 m its velocity (V) will be lower than 35 km/h. This number can be more dramatic: a minimum of 12 km/h was reported for old generation trucks by Walton and Lee (1975), for the same displacement, but with the starting velocity of 75 km/h. This velocity will limit the flow capacity of the tunnel. Therefore, such value of gradient for ramps is not acceptable.

7.1 The rock of Vitória Bay

The rock of Vitória Bay was poorly studied and the results was assessed from 5 boreholes tests.

The sediments over the rock are loose sand and soft clay. Prandina (2011) presented a seminar showing the characteristics of the project (DER, 2010) to local the technical community. The event were released by the Espírito Santo board of Engineers (CREA-ES) and also by the press.

One of the issues of the NATM tunnel proposed was the competent rock for its development and for the underground works in a subaquatic and very high water table pressure.

Additionally, the construction method needs a minimum stability in a fractured massif, the competent strata to achieve this minimum safety is there between 51 to 52 m.

7.2 The land reclamation and environment

Prandina (2011) showed also that a land reclamation, the green area in Figure 7, was an important issue of the project of the NATM tunnel proposed by DER (2010).

This importance is due to the road traffic project of the NATM tunnel did not adopted the binary Paulino Muller and João Santos (late Alberto Torres) avenues available aligned with the tunnel axis to feed the tunnel (Figure 8). The PDTU (1998) stated that this binary would feed the connection. This land reclamation will use the area between the Fumaça island and Nossa Senhora dos Navegantes Avenue to build an embankment to settle a new road system for the access of the NATM tunnel proposed. The land reclamation area can be seen in green in the Figure 7 (DER, 2010).

8 THE POSSIBLE SECOND CHANGE

The second probable change in the connection for Vitória and Vila Velha tunnel can occur because the Immersed Tunnel method has all the appropriate credentials to be the tunnel construction method for this purpose.

The Immersed Tunnel will avoid the excessive gradients of the ramps, the main issue of the NATM proposed tunnel. Because of the smaller depth of the Immersed solution, also the horizontal design will be shorter, and so the construction will face much less uncertainly, and so costs.

These questions were showed by Prandina (2011), showing the different concepts of the tunnel proposed by Kneib and Prandina (2004) and the proposal of the Espírito Santo government (DER, 2010).

Figure 7. Land reclamation to accommodate the road access of the NATM tunnel (DER, 2010)

8.1 The 1st International Seminar in Brazil

The first International Seminar in Brazil in Immersed Tunnels have been presented in June of 2012 as part of the disclosure process of the tunnel solutions available to the project of Vitória and Vila Velha connection and took place at the CREA-ES auditorium.

This seminar was also de 2nd Seminar in underground works in Vitória, so called “Túneis & Subaquatic Constructions” considering the seminar “Túneis para Vitória” (2008) as the first. Prandina (2012a) presented some detailed procedures for the construction of the Immersed Tunnel solution and its advanced sealing systems.

This seminar had the presentations of Peter van Westendorp and Hans de Wit as released by the press (Prandina, 2012b). It had been shown that 70% to 80% of the costs of construction work of a Immersed Tunnel can be hired from the local companies, taking 70% as the minimum.

Once more, the headline in the press by Prandina (2012b) called the attention of the society showing that this construction method would lead to a cheaper cost for the connection between Vitória and Vila Velha.

8.2 The Santos-Guarujá Tunnel Project

The Santos-Guarujá tunnel project has been presented by Rocha (2008). This project also has been preceded by a changed in a pre-announced bridge solution for the same purpose.

The feasibility study of the Santos-Guarujá tunnel considered 13 different proposals. After a pre-qualification, two proposals (D and E) have been elected as the best and each one received a comprehensive cost estimation.

The tunnel is composed by 6 traffic lanes and a gallery for cycle lane and pedestrians (Figure 8). The tunnel line itself has 1320 m according to Dersa (2013), and 1800 m in total length considering the accesses.

Figure 8. The Santos-Guarujá cross section (Dersa, 2013)

9 CONCLUSION

As conclusions, the most important quote is that either for tunnels or for bridges, to come up with the best solution which fits to the public interest of environmental issues, safety, efficiency and economy the experts in each area have to dedicate the state-of-the-art in a competent feasibility study.

This work has showed that, even though the culture and the environment in Espírito Santo state for a new, better and efficient tunnel solution is not initially receptive, a good strategy based on correct communication and technical reports released to the society has allowed to include the tunnel as a considered solution for the connection between Vitória and Vila Velha.

The resume of the phases which can describe the Vitória-Vila Velha tunnel endeavor is:

- An initial hostile scenario for tunnel solution was established in ES until 2008;

- A good strategy has released for society the tunnel solutions and possibilities;
- Tunnel has become the final solution for the connection between Vitória and Vila Velha;
- A second change in the connection solutions from the proposed NATM Tunnel to the Immersed Tunnel might bring the state-of-the-art of the tunnel industry of subaquatic connections to the process;

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REFERENCES

- Anselmo Neto, L.; Guedes, N. L. S.; Bertolde, A. I. 2009. Análise de capacidade de vias na cidade de Vitória – O caso da 3ª Ponte. Companhia Brasileira de Trens Urbanos, Acervo Digital, Rio de Janeiro, RJ. <http://www.cbtu.gov.br/monografia/2009/trabalhos/artigos/engenharia/6_260_AC.pdf>. Accessed in 10 Oct. 2013.
- Assis, A.P. 2008. Métodos de Execução de Túneis. In: *Seminário Túneis para Vitória*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 14p.
- Casilhas, A. 2007. Túnel da Baía de Vitória. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 20 May 2007, p.14.
- Castro, R. 2013. Só 20% dos veículos esperados passam pela alça da 3ª Ponte. *Gazetaonline*, Vitória, <http://gazetaonline.globo.com/_conteudo/2013/08/noticias/cidades/1458271-so-20-dos-veiculos-esperados-passam-pela-alca-da-3-ponte.html>, accessed in 20 Oct. 2013.
- Caus, A. L.; Santos, J. F. 2008. A rota do transporte coletivo. *Revista do Comdevit – Conselho Metropolitano de Desenvolvimento da Grande Vitória*. Nº 1. Vitória: Instituto Jones dos Santos Neves, p. 16.
- Damasceno, F. 2011. Programa de Mobilidade Urbana – BRT Grande Vitória. In: *Proceedings of the III Seminário de Transportes Urbanos*. Vila Velha: ASEVILA <asevila.org.br/index.php?id=/sala_de_imprensa/eventos/materia.php&cd_matia=2051>, accessed 21 Oct 2013.
- DaMatta, R. 2008. *Relatório Final do Projeto Igualdade no Trânsito*. Porto Alegre: Atena Consultoria. 204p.

- DER, 2010. *Edital de concorrência Nº 32/2010*. Vitória: Secretaria de Transportes e Obras Públicas do Estado do Espírito Santo. 50p.
- Dersa, 2013. *Túnel Submerso Santos-Guarujá*. São Paulo: Secretaria de Logística e Transportes do Estado de São Paulo. 69p.
- Ford, C.R. 1997. *Immersed Tunnel Techniques 2*. London: Thomas Telford. 359p.
- Hartung, P.G.. 2009. Túnel Vitória-Vila Velha vai sair, mas com pedágio. *A Gazeta*. Vitória, 21 Mar 2000, p.3.
- IBGE, 2010. *Censo demográfico*. São Paulo: Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística. <www.ibge.gov.br>, accessed 21 Oct 2013.
- Jazra, G. 2012. DNIT abre concorrência para reforma da Segunda Ponte de Vitória. *Piniweb*: São Paulo, <piniweb.pini.com.br/construcao/infra-estrutura/dnit-abre-concorrancia-para-reforma-da-segunda-ponte-de-vitoria-273511-1.aspx>, accessed 20 Oct 2013.
- Kneib, E. C. 2001a. A Proposta da Quarta Ligação Vitória-Vila Velha - Túnel Imerso. *Monograph*: (BsC in Urbanism and Architecture) – Federal University of Espírito Santo, Vitória, 120p.
- Kneib, E. C. 2001b. Túnel imerso para ligar Vitória à Vila Velha. *Revista Tópicos*. Vitória: Conselho Regional de Engenharia e Arquitetura do Espírito Santo. 45p
- Kneib, E.C.; Prandina, J. R. 2004. A proposta da quarta ligação Vitória-Vila Velha em túnel imerso. In: *1º Congresso Brasileiro de Túneis e Estruturas Subterrâneas*, São Paulo: CBT/ABMS, p. 68.
- Kneib, E. C. 2005. Túnel na Baía de Vitória. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 01 Jul. 2005, p.8.
- Kneib, E. C. 2006. Arquiteta propõe túnel até Vila Velha. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 31 May 2006, p.13.
- Kneib, E. C. 2008. Quarta ligação Vitória-Vila Velha em Túnel Imerso. In: *Seminário Túneis para Vitória*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 14p.
- Kneib, E. C. 2011. Túnel e mobilidade. *A Gazeta*, Vitória, 02 Jan. 2011, p.30.
- Kochen, R. 2008. Túneis Imersos: avanços e soluções. In: *Seminário Túneis para Vitória*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 14p.
- Martins, F. 2008. Túnel é a melhor solução. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 28 Ago 2008, p.12.
- Oliveira, J. 2008. Será que desta vez o trânsito vai fluir mesmo? *Folha Vitória*. Vitória: <folhavoria.com.br/site/?target=coluna&cid=12&pagina=65&post=3500>, accessed 20 Oct 2013.
- Pandini, A. 2007. Carros de passeio lotam ruas e transportam poucos no Estado. *Folha Vitória*. Vitória, <folhavoria.com.br/site/?target=coluna&cid=11>, accessed 21 Oct 2013.
- Pausem, K.B.T.; Louzada, S.S.S. 2012. Mobilidade urbana na Grande Vitória e suas questões. *Revista Científica da Faculdade Cenequista de Vila Velha, Vitória*. Vol. 4. Vitória: FACEVV. 39p.
- PDTU, 1998. *Plano Diretor de Transportes Urbanos da Região Metropolitana da Grande Vitória*. Vitória: Secretaria de Transportes e Obras Públicas do Espírito Santo. 373p.
- PMV, 2007 *Pesquisa origem-destino na Grande Vitória: como anda nossa gente*. Vitória: Instituto Jones dos Santos Neves. 122p.
- Prandina, J. R. 2008a. Túnel pronto em 3 anos. *A Tribuna*. Vitória: 11 Dec. 2008, p.9.
- Prandina, J. R. 2008b. Trânsito faz usuários terem custo bilionário na 3ª Ponte. *A Gazeta*. Vitória: 11 Dec. 2008, p.4.
- Prandina, J. R. 2008c. Seis túneis contra congestionamentos. *A Tribuna*. Vitória: 08 Oct. 2008, p.12.
- Prandina, J. R. 2008d. Túneis para Vitória. In: *Seminário Túneis para Vitória*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 14p.
- Prandina, J. R. 2009a. Ilhados na ilha de Vitória. *Projeto Urbano*, Nº 2, Vitória: Urban Engenharia.
- Prandina, J. R. 2009b. Solução para o trânsito é criar novas vias. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 11 Feb. 2009, p.25.
- Prandina, J. R. 2010a. Túnel para desafogar a Reta da Penha. *A Tribuna*. Vitória: 16 Dez. 2010, p.12.
- Prandina, J. R. 2010b. *Proposta para projeto básico e parceria público-privada: Túnel Vitória-Vila Velha*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 15 Dez. 2008, p.12.
- Prandina, J. R. 2011. *A quarta ligação de Vitória e Vila Velha*. Vitória: CREA-ES, 44p.
- Prandina, J. R. 2012a. Feasibility of the Immersed Tunnel method for the connections of Vitória, In: *1º Seminário Internacional de Túneis Imersos - Túneis e Construções Subaquáticas*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 8p.
- Prandina, J. R. 2012b. Solução mais barata para túnel. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 22 Aug. 2012, p.11.
- Proscholdt, E.; Spinassé, F.; Cezini, K. 2013. Projeto da quarta ponte. *A Tribuna*. Vitória, 27 Sept. 2013, p.3.
- Rocha, A. 2012. Quarta Ponte no Espírito Santo terá 1,4 mil metros de extensão. *Piniweb*: São Paulo, <<http://piniweb.pini.com.br/construcao/infra-estrutura/quarta-ponte-no-espírito-santo-tera-14-mil-metros-de-262903-1.aspx>>, accessed 20 Oct 2013.
- Rocha, H. C. 2008. Túnel Santos Guarujá. In: *Seminário Túneis para Vitória*. Vitória: Urban Engenharia, 14p.
- Sá, C. 2013. Quarta ponte: obra só a partir de julho que vem. *A Gazeta*, Vitória, 27 Sept. 2013, p.3.
- Walton, C.W.; Lee, C.E. 1975. *Speed of vehicles on grades*. Austin: Center for Highway Research, The University of Texas at Austin. 164p.